

FUNDAMENTALS OF MECHANISMS OF FORMATION OF ETHNO-PEDAGOGICAL PERSONNEL IN STUDENTS OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Ethnopedagogy also maintains ties with ethnosociology. This science examines the behavior of representatives of a nation in relation to the surrounding society.

Studying the basics of ethno-pedagogy, parents, students and teachers should understand its content. It has several main directions that will allow you to accept this new knowledge.

The organizational and active direction of this subject includes the study of basic knowledge in the field of education of the young generation. The child and his behavior are both an object and a subject in the educational process. The structural content includes the functions of education, for example, the development of mental abilities, the promotion of ethics and aesthetics.

To be completed factors - history , nature , religion. Ethnopedagogy concept contained _ _ structural of the elements one of education methods and are tools . Study of the process in the center personality development idea and him done increase enters _

Presentation done science in education too to educate organize reach mean caught _ Family , community , person and whole of humanity mutually cooperation forms and vital of activity role learns _ Ethnopedagogy own in the composition people teachers examples uses _ Even they are famous teachers , their thoughts and statements , public characters , parents and even bigger children to be can _ This of directions to each other the addition of social responsible person characteristic and moral characteristic moral properties have to be contribution adds _

To their goals reach and problems solution to do of ethno- pedagogy for certain tools is used . They are science separately in the direction separate standing a little to himself is typical . Like this styles , but a little different in style application possible and modern pedagogy. Ethno-pedagogy, as well as this to methods his own unique features present is enough

This to the children information more more convenient in the form to give enable gives _ Such of methods interest in its assimilation process efficient factor is considered Through ethno -pedagogy knowledge of transmission main approaches - explanation , reliable and example _ Also like this educational requirements , agreement , order , belief , request and of advice methods mean catch usual is the case .

Exercise to do and exercise please do _ or dream to do active is used . If need If so , complain to do , insult , approval or advice get can _ During training surface came to the situation looking at it or another ethno-pedagogical method is used .

Good result get for present done all methods right apply need _ Of this for of the child psyche or their of the group characteristics , as well as children each other with , society with mutually of relations features account take _ Of this for learning factors account is taken .

Ethno- pedagogy concept study , it bring up factors attention focus it is necessary If today's in the day in schools teachable usual sciences in learning factors scientists , others of scientists research if , then another basics ethnic education with depend _

This on the ground of education factor - history , nature and religion. of the country each one sure mental reserve this kind of of education basis is considered That's why for , one in the state living each for one person another of the factors not used .

Well , for example , the population of Germany for the population of Japan education in the direction of application possible not _ All nations same pattern _ with live they can't . This theory or in practice possible not _ Therefore , educate _

to himself special features , daily marriage style , centuries during appear has been traditions to ethno-pedagogical factors own effect is showing .

During training this to himself special features attention taken need _ Har one in ethno education duties and goals superiority does _ They are teaching common means , approaches and in the factors is expressed .

Ethno- pedagogical education in the process efficient direction is considered His possibilities different , they are different how of the child attention drag can _ First , communication tools education tools applies . This in process children ethics and to morality according to the environment with how contact to do they learn Also communication _ own thoughts , feelings right to express help gives to the teacher certain to the situation suitable methods to apply possibility gives _

Ethno- pedagogy the most efficient of means one plays _ Various people games , events all students study to the process attraction does _ With that together , they are a team spirit with struggle , society one part to be for much it becomes easier . Har one a person one of the whole one part _ In the game participation doing each one child continues which common in process own role feel can _

Ethnopedagogy tool very is diverse . Theirs most of them is creativity . Oral words , boredom intelligence teaches . Ancient to us since time immemorial fell different stories _ of our people of wisdom real warehouse . Children for is available has been in the form behavior norms , environment with mutually relationship about various information _ given _ Legends and legends you difficult situations too strong , wise and capable to be teaches . They are common goodness for goodness to do need about they speak This educational tools to a person trust and trust than more effect shows .

Ethno- pedagogy again one efficient tool is this work _ Children's thematic crafts , food , costumes from creating satisfied _ He is creative manifestation that 's enough while of the child own his opinion expression to reach possibility gives _ Of these all of them of a person each bilaterally development contribution adds _

Children own history , nationality , family and each other respect to do learns _ This modern our society for very important _

Modern ethno-pedagogy is indeed too worthy person to educate able has been special science _ His actions common prosperity and to development to reach is directed .

Rapidly changing of technologies modern in the world a person historical the past with connection loses . People centuries during work issued of morality main principles they forget Modern society natural environment no who does natural resources contained _ _ to the predator converted . Because of this today's in the day very important the issue is the person own the world and society cover received to nature has been responsible attitude education _

Last ten in annuals we important technological discoveries demonstration we did Natural looting of resources do , own type , family , nationality against broken ideas in our lives more more and more more is being observed . Ethnopedagogy , young generation attention on our planet all alive to existing ones respect with in relation to be calls _ Centuries during is available has been this thin system today's in the day of humanity constant attacks under remains _ of the planet face changed stands , sometimes non-refundable .

This our to our morality , our our action for responsibility to the feeling appeal which ethno pedagogy. This our of our society each one representative solidarity the feeling as well as the decision consequences about to know means _ Around us to the world right relationship our family , our society , our nation for deep respect with begins . High moral man in the world the most near around and all creatures appreciates _ This to us of the people wisdom teaches . Our ancestors our ancestors ancient has known since time immemorial .

Noisy , fast changing the world us our mind with to fill need has been the most important things from memory does not issue need _ If our history if we forget , our ancestors instructions us inevitable respectively to the abyss fall , real the way lost we will be That's why ethno- pedagogy for family , too social of education

indispensable part to be need _ After all , he is not the only one each one a person for , but the whole society for necessary has been the most important personal qualities educates .

Shown of science main concepts seeing out , ethno-pedagogical education in the field important direction that it is our emphasis can _ It is effective from tools uses and young generation in education very good goals looks _ Emergency approach of children new information better acceptance to do , creative abilities to develop possibility gives _ Environment with mutually Ethno-pedagogy is ethical in relations and high moral qualities to develop help gives _ With that together , children own around the world .

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